

Accurate Measurement of Grain Legume Crop Yields

Problem

Accurate crop yield measurements are essential to: (a) quantify farm productivity; (b) compare the effects of different farm management practices; and (c) provide key inputs for ecosystem service indicators, such as crop nitrogen balance. However, many farms estimate yields only at whole-farm level, based on the total volume of produce stored, or sold. This approach does not allow yields to be measured at field level, meaning differences in performance between fields, including for crop sequences, remain hidden. As a result, yield variability and its consequences, are rarely understood, limiting opportunities for targeted improvements in productivity and sustainability.

Solution

The accounting methods described here provide a clear set of practical rules to ensure crop yields are measured accurately using standard commercial farm equipment. This method aims to support farmers and advisors in collecting reliable, field-level yield data, without the need for specialised research machinery.

Benefits

Accurate, field level yield measurements make it possible to better quantify and optimise the benefits of pulse crops for subsequent crops in the rotation.

Practical recommendation

Measuring the yield of seed crops generally falls into two approaches, use of a weigh bridge and/or use of a yield mapping combine.

- **The weighbridge method**
 1. Record the harvest area (ha) using a good quality GPS tool or a measuring wheel to measure the perimeter of harvested areas.
 2. Weigh harvested seed from that area (metric tons) by accurately weighing trailers before and after harvest.
 3. Measure the percentage moisture content of the seed (% MC) and adjust the yield to a standard value, and usually 15 % MC (see Equation 1).
- **The yield mapping combine: method mapping grain yields harvested using a combine harvester**
 1. Calibrate the harvesters yield monitor using the manufacturer's instructions. This may involve calibrating based on values taken over a weighbridge.

Applicability box

Theme

Legume productivity measurements

Keywords

Yield; field trials; productivity

Context

Arable systems

Application time

Harvest

Required time

NA

Period of impact

NA

Equipment

Combine harvester & access to weighbridge, or yield mapping combine harvester or quadrat

Best in

Grain legumes

- Harvest the known crop area. Avoid non-full headers if the intention is to also measure harvested area with the combine yield monitor. If harvesting a trial area, keep to a constant speed and try to harvest the whole trial under the same conditions and on the same day. Harvest in line with the tramlines for trial plots.

Key considerations

- Measuring yields only in central parts of a field can overestimate overall field yield, as lower yielding headlands and field boundaries are excluded. While this approach may inflate absolute yield values, it can still be appropriate when the aim is to compare the relative performance of different treatments under similar conditions.
- Harvesting over a weighbridge, or yield mapping, can also be used for whole crop harvests. However, where these approaches are not feasible, quadrat sampling can provide an alternative method to track field productivity. This involves measuring yield from multiple quadrat (up to 1 m²) cuts and extrapolating the results to a standard unit area (e.g., per hectare). Care is needed here and enough samples must be taken from several locations to ensure within-field variability is considered, and biased estimates avoided. As with grain yields, wholecrop yields should be standardised to 15 % MC (using dry quadrat weights); that is, after drying at 70 °C for several days and until constant dry weight is achieved).

$$\text{Yield (tonnes per Ha @ standard Moisture Content) = } \frac{\text{net weight of harvested grain tonnes}}{\text{area harvested (Ha)}} * \left(100 - \frac{\text{measured seed Moisture Content}}{\text{Standard Moisture Content}} \right)$$

Equation 1. Calculation for standardising moisture content of harvested pulse seed.

Further information

For more information on designing fair field trials and measuring accurate yields see the [ADAS Guide to Farmers' Crop Trials](#) and [On-farm trials: five principles for success](#).

About this practice abstract

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